

How Organizations Should View Reskilling and Upskilling The Workforce

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Abstract

Uncertainty is a significant word that every individual will need to comprehend. The world we live in today have demonstrated how uncertainty is becoming a norm. Various reports are indicating that millions of workforce needs to be ready for the transition which is taking place in the job market globally. The workforce needs to accept that reskilling and up skilling is needed if they want to be relevant and employable

Background

Every minute there is new technologies emerging due to digitization and it impacts the business and global economy directly. Having the talent to support the eco system is becoming challenging for global business and organisations are seeking way to find a solution. Literatures have indicated that the concept of “Reskilling and Upskilling” is forcing innovative learning solutions in schools and higher education institutions. In additions, training companies are trying in filling the gaps that the schools and higher education institutions are not able to deliver. The days of going to schools and universities and getting a certificate and degree is constantly debated.

What are Reskilling and Upskilling?

To answer the question, let’s view what is actually “Reskilling and Upskilling”. Reskilling is to learn entirely new skills sets that will lead to new career positions while Upskilling is to learn new skills that will support to improve your current position. As an example, an individual have been working in an automotive industry for years and intents to move to higher education as an educator. Although he or she might have the experiences and qualification but chances being employed in higher education is still a 50/50. Therefore, the individual needs to be prepared to be reskilled by learning entirely new set of skills that is required to execute his role at the higher education institutions.

The advantage he or she will have is by incorporating the industry experiences with the new skill sets that have been acquired. On the other hand, upskilling is when an individual is working as a lecture and learns new set of skills that will improve his/her performance within the organisation so that the deliverable are up to date. This also can lead for the individual to be promoted within the institutions. Therefore, before thinking of producing talents and increasing the workforce, the basic knowledge regards to “Reskilling and Upskilling” is important.

How and What to Think?

Organizations have to think carefully and design their future business strategies and workforce planning. Questions such as: Is my workforce in my business need to be upskilled and why it has to be done? What impacts it will create by doing so? Will that bring more business opportunities since my business has the resources and upskilled workforce? Were they upskilled based on the technology changes and is my organization is prepared to constantly train them due the never ending technology innovations? Will they be replaced by automation? If they need to be reskilled, will that create new ventures within my business? Will the Covid -19 Pandemic force my business to shut down after investing on “Reskilling and Upskilling” the workforce?

Consequences of Ignoring

These questions may sound simple however, we have to understand that global workforce is passing through changes constantly. If an organization is not ready to realize the changes around it, then it may no longer be existed. This will lead to unemployment and failures of payments such as housing loans, car loans, study loans, credit cards, medical insurance, food supplies and basic needs for families. This will lead to unimaginable consequences. In addition, the future graduates will not be able to get a job and will not be able to payback the education loans. These further impacts the financial institutions and government needs to come up with stimulus packages and bailouts. Does the government have enough money to do so? One think is sure, economists are not able to provide exactly the economic damage from the Covid -19 Pandemic. Various reports indicated that approximately 3.5 Trillion U.S Dollars is lost to begin with.

Taking Action

Therefore, it is a responsibility of every stakeholders when regards to “Reskilling and Upskilling”. They should be able to convey clear message to the overall society. As an example, Institutions are created with a purpose, and the purpose drives the institutions to achieve the targets. So what are their targets? Recruiting students to increase their profits or having awareness of the demands of business changes. Hence to recap, how organization

should view reskilling and upskilling the workforce is significant. There is a call for responsibility of today's leaders and education and corporate organisations.